

Community Satisfaction Index in the Livable Home Program by Exxonmobil Cepu Limited (EMCL) in Bojonegoro, East Java, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: Bojonegoro Regency is one of the regions in the East Java province of Indonesia. The Bojonegoro Regency government has 17 main priority programs, one of which is related to renovating poor people's houses to become livable houses. To achieve this program, of course, cooperation from all parties is needed, including the private sector, to contribute to accelerating program implementation, in this case EMCL contributes to the community empowerment program in the form of a livable housing program. This research uses descriptive research. Descriptive research is research that examines a group of people, objects, conditions, systems of thought, or an event in the present. Meanwhile, the approach in this research uses a quantitative approach. From the results of analysis based on data from questionnaires that have been distributed to 30 respondents who are beneficiaries of the program, data on score values per element of community satisfaction can be obtained. and it can be explained that 6 elements have a weight value of A with the SS criteria (Strongly agree) which shows the meaning of satisfaction is very satisfied. Based on the results of the analysis of community satisfaction index beneficiaries of the habitable housing program by EMCL in partnership with PC Fatayat NU Bojonegoro, the 6 indicator elements show that The community is very satisfied with the existing program.

KEYWORDS: Livable houses, community empowerment programs, community satisfaction index.

I. INTRODUCTION

Housing is a basic need that is very important for every human being like food and clothing. This is very fundamental for human welfare, survival and health (Ridlo, 2011). Therefore, housing is one of the best indicators of a person's standard of living and his place in society. Various research on housing problems (Sastra et al, 2006; Budiharjo, 2009) says that the housing problem cannot be solved completely, there must be regular reviews of housing policies, housing policy finances, encouragement of the use of local materials, and the provision of cheap houses in places urban and rural. The role of the private sector is needed in this housing problem for low income groups (LIG) (Dimitra et al, 2012). To overcome poverty in rural areas and sub-districts, especially houses that are uninhabitable, the Government is holding an Uninhabitable Houses (RTLH) program for the poor. With the hope that poor people can provide comfortable and safe housing. improving the health quality of the residential environment for poor families and of course improving the quality of life of the poor.

As we all know, the Bojonegoro Regency Government has 17 main priority programs, one of which is related to renovating poor people's houses to become livable houses. To achieve this program, of course cooperation from all parties is needed, including the private sector to contribute to accelerating program implementation, in this case EMCL. EMCL is partnering with PC Fatayat NU Bojonegoro to implement the LIVABLE HOMES program with a target of

30 housing units. The details are 10 houses in Punggur Village, Purwosari District, 10 houses in Grebegan Village, Kalitidu District and 10 houses in Sumengko Village, Kalitidu District, Bojonegoro District. The program runs for 4 (four) months with funds of Rp. 17,000,000 (seventeen million rupiah) for 1 house unit. The implementation of this program is carried out by implementing a community empowerment strategy, which is supported by increasing capacity through training and mentoring. The approach used is a participatory process, which is an approach that facilitates the process of inspiring and empowering local communities to analyze their own problems and needs as well as ways to solve them. This method was chosen because this method can foster a democratic and learning atmosphere, apart from that, this method can foster a sense of ownership of the program being carried out because it is always involved in every process carried out. However, this method certainly influences the results of home products received by the community, so that it will influence the level of community satisfaction with the program that has been running..

Based on the discussion above, it is necessary to conduct an analysis regarding the level of satisfaction of the people who receive the benefits of the livable housing program by EMCL in partnership with PC Fatayat NU Bojonegoro in Punggur Village, Purwosari District, Grebegan Village, Kalitidu District and Sumengko Village, Kalitidu District, Bojonegoro District) East Java, Indonesia.

An index is a composite measure for a variable. Measuring satisfaction through several dimensions or aspects. In this research, each statement is given the same weight. This is because researchers have not determined a strong reason to witness the unequal weighting of statements in each dimension (Moenir, 2008)

According to Mustafa, index comes from the Latin word *indicare*, which means pointing. An index provides an indication of written works that have been published on a particular subject, either in magazine form or in the form of other documents

J. Paul Peter and Jerry C. Olson in the book *Usmara* (2003) define satisfaction and dissatisfaction as a comparison between performance expectations before purchasing and the performance perceptions received by consumers after purchasing. This means that if the performance expectations before purchasing are greater than the performance received after purchasing, then it can be said that consumers are experiencing dissatisfaction. On the other hand, if the performance expectations before purchasing are smaller than the performance perceptions before purchasing, then consumers experience satisfaction.

Oliver in Husain Umar's book (2003), defines customer satisfaction as a post-purchase evaluation, in which the perception of the performance of the selected product/service meets or even exceeds expectations before purchase. This means that if the perception of performance cannot meet expectations, what will happen is customer dissatisfaction. Crosby also defines, dissatisfaction with the final product or service of an organization is called trouble with quality (Philip, 1986). Thus, dissatisfaction with an organization's product or service can cause problems with the quality of that product or service.

From several definitions of satisfaction according to the experts above, it can be concluded that satisfaction is a person's feeling of happiness or disappointment as a result of a comparison between perceived performance (experienced reality) and consumer expectations. Customer satisfaction includes a comparison between expectations and the performance received. Because customers are consumers who receive the results of the producer's work, it is the customer who determines whether a product or service is of quality or not.

The main basis for the Community Satisfaction Index Survey is the Regulation of the Minister of State Apparatus Empowerment and Bureaucratic Reform of Indonesia Number 14 of 2017. Article 1 explains that public service providers are required to conduct regular community satisfaction surveys at least once a year. The Community Satisfaction Index is data and information about the level of community satisfaction obtained from the results of qualitative and quantitative measurements of community opinions in obtaining services from government officials by

comparing needs and expectations. The indicators used in the Community Satisfaction Index study are as follows:

1. Input

Input indicators measure the amount of resources used, such as budget (funds), human resources, equipment, materials and other inputs, which are used to carry out activities. The derivative of this indicator is the amount of budget distributed to Beneficiaries through the Village implementation team.

2. Proses

A derivative of the process indicator is the selection, verification and data validation process of potential beneficiaries

3. Output

Output indicators are used to measure output that directly results from the implementation of an activity, both physical and non-physical. Derived output indicators are Verification from assistants regarding the number of active beneficiaries in the study location, Training from assistants in budget management to improve the welfare of beneficiary families through livable houses, determination training schedule for increasing skills from the accompanying team, developing and guaranteeing the usefulness of decent housing.

4. Results

Results indicators are used to measure the achievements of various activities in a program that have been completed or indicators that reflect the functioning of the output of various activities in the medium term. Derived from the outcome indicators are the number of beneficiaries from the verification results, the implementation of training from assistants in budget management for habitable houses, the availability of determining training schedules to improve the skills of the implementation team and guarantees of the usefulness of habitable houses for the beneficiary community.

5. Benefit

The derivative of the benefit indicator is the benefit of the livable housing program for the welfare of the beneficiary families.

6. Impact

Impact indicators show the influence, both positive and negative, resulting from the implementation of policies/programs/activities and the assumptions that have been used. The derivative of the impact indicator is an increase in welfare figures for medium-term beneficiary families.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses descriptive research. Descriptive research is research that examines a group of people, objects, conditions, systems of thought, or an event in the present. Meanwhile, the approach in this research uses a quantitative approach. Quantitative research basically emphasizes analysis on numerical data (numbers) which are processed

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using statistical methods. So it can make it easier for writers to explain the raw data obtained.

Research instruments are tools or facilities used by researchers in collecting research data so that their work becomes easier, in the sense of being more careful, complete, systematic so that it is easier to process the data. The research instrument used in this research was a questionnaire. A questionnaire is a tool in the form of questions that must be answered by each respondent, which is used to determine the satisfaction index score of the beneficiary community. The questionnaire used is a closed questionnaire, where each question item has an alternative answer provided and the respondent only chooses one of the many alternatives provided. Respondents' answers were in the form of choices from five existing alternatives in the form of Favorable (positive) and Unfavorable (negative).

The measurement technique for this research instrument uses the Likert's Summated Rating (LSR) measuring instrument with a measurement scale of alternative favorable and unfavorable answers. To measure the satisfaction index of the beneficiary community in the research questionnaire (question numbers: 1,3,5,7,9,11) the answers were: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Mild (M), Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD). Meanwhile, to measure Pro-Abes in the research questionnaire (question numbers: 2,4,6,8,10,12) the answers were Very Important (VI), Important (I), Less Important (LI), Not Important (NI), Very Unimportant (VU).

Table 1 Community Satisfaction Index Instrument Item Scores

Kriteria	Score	
	Favorable	Unfavorable
Strongly Agree (SA)	5	1
Agree (A)	4	2
Mild (M)	3	3
Disagree (D),	2	4
Strongly Disagree (SD)	1	5

Tabel 2 Skor Item Instrument Program rumah layak huni

Kriteria	Score	
	Favorable	Unfavorable
Very Important (VI),	5	1
Important (I),	4	2
Less Important (LI),	3	3
Not Important (NI),	2	4
Very Unimportant (VU).	1	5

The population in this study was 30 people, consisting of all families who were beneficiaries of the livable housing program.

This research applies purposive sampling, which is a sampling technique used by researchers if the researcher has certain considerations in taking the sample. Because it only

consisted of 30 people, all of them were used as respondents in this research.

The data used is primary data resulting from distributing questionnaires. The data analysis technique is carried out using the average value of each service element. The research data management carried out is as follows:

a. Editing

After the questionnaire has been filled in and returned by the respondent to the writer, the writer will then examine the completeness of filling out the questionnaire, if there are things that are incomplete both in the identity and answers given by the respondent, then the writer will contact them again to be perfected so that the questionnaire is considered valid. used for data processing.

b. Coding

Coding is the activity of coding data in the form of letters into data in the form of numbers (numbers), for favorable and unfavorable questions. The code used is in accordance with the discussion in the questionnaire.

c. Data tabulation

After the data is collected, a tabulation stage will be carried out in the form of a table which creates information from the data, including; The data on each item is given a score so that it can later be processed in numerical form and will be adjusted to the analysis technique that will be used. The 6 elements studied in calculating the Community Satisfaction Index, each service element has the same weighting according to the formula:

$$\text{average} = \frac{\text{Number of weights}}{\text{Number of elements}} = \frac{1}{N}$$

Dimana:

X = number of elements surveyed

N = The value weight of each element

Table 3. Perception values and IKM intervals

Weight value	Interval value	conversion interval value	Respondent weight interval value	Category		
				Satisfaction	Performance	
1	E	1.00 - 1.79	20.00 - 35.99	127.00 - 228.59	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very Important (VI),
2	D	1.80 - 2.59	36.00 - 51.99	228.60 - 330.19	Agree (A)	Important (I),
3	C	2.60 - 3.39	52.00 - 67.99	330.20 - 431.79	Mild (M)	Less Important (LI),
4	B	3.40 - 4.19	68.00 - 83.99	431.80 - 533.39	Disagree	Not Import

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5	A	4.20 - 5.00	84.00 - 100.00	533.40 - 635.00	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Very Unimportant (VU).
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The average value per service element is multiplied by the weighted average value. So, the weighted average value per element is obtained. Meanwhile, the combined index value for each service unit is multiplied by the same weight and the result is the index value of community satisfaction with the program.

III.RESULTS

The analysis of the satisfaction index of the beneficiary community towards the livable housing program in Punggur Village, Purwosari District, Grebegan Village, Kalitidu District and Sumengko Village, Kalitidu District, Bojonegoro District is explained as follows:

From the results of the questionnaire that was distributed to 30 respondents who were beneficiaries of the program, data on score values per element of community satisfaction can be obtained as shown in table 4 below

Table 4. Score Value Per Satisfaction Element

No	Element	Value	Average
1	Input	147	4,9
2	Process	135	4,5
3	Ouput	145	4,8
4	Result	145	4,8
5	Benefit	148	4,9
6	Impact	149	4,9

(Source: Analysis results, 2022)

A. Next, the conversion value of the Satisfaction Index for the people who receive the benefits of the livable housing program to the service quality category is based on the index shown in the following table:

Table 5. Interval Value, Conversion and Satisfaction Weight

No	Element	Interval value	Conversion interval value	Weight value	Criteria
1	Input	4,9	98	A	SA
2	Process	4,5	90	A	SA
3	Ouput	4,8	96,7	A	SA
4	Result	4,8	96,7	A	SA
5	Benefit	4,9	98,7	A	SA
6	Impact	4,9	99	A	SA

(Source: Analysis results, 2022)

From table 5 it can be explained that 6 elements have a weight value of A with SS criteria (Strongly agree) which shows the meaning of satisfaction, very satisfied..

IV.CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of an analysis of the satisfaction index of the beneficiary community towards the habitable housing program by ExxonMobil Cepu Ltd (EMCL) in partnership with PC Fatayat NU Bojonegoro in Punggur Village, Purwosari District, Grebegan Village, Kalitidu District and Sumengko Village, Kalitidu District, Bojonegoro District, East Java, Indonesia from 6 elements indicators show that the community is very satisfied with the existing program.

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